

Education Quarterly Reviews

Turnadi, Tri, Sasongko, Rambat Nur, Kristiawan, Muhammad, Oktaria, Sheren Dwi, And Susanto, Edy (2021), The Role of School Leadership in Improving Teachers and Employee Work Disciplines in SMA Negeri 2 Lahat. In: Education Quarterly Reviews, Vol.4, No.2, 138-146.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.04.02.205

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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The Role of School Leadership in Improving Teachers and Employee Work Disciplines

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Abstract

This study aims to determine and describe the role of principal leadership in improving the work discipline of teachers and employees and to find out what obstacles are obstacles to the role of principal leadership in improving the work discipline of teachers and employees at SMA Negeri 2 Lahat. This research is a descriptive qualitative research type and uses purposive sampling technique. There are five roles of the Principal and two obstacles faced by the Principal in improving the work discipline of teachers and employees. From the results of the research shows that the principal of SMA Negeri 2 Lahat carries out the role as a leader by planning and deliberating, as a manager by creating collaboration between teachers and employees, as educators by preparing learning program plans as administrators by managing facilities and infrastructure as well as financial administration, motivators. by providing motivation with a conducive school environment. The obstacles faced by school principals in improving the work discipline of teachers and employees are teachers and employees who are less disciplined in carrying out their duties so that they are also difficult to improve their work discipline, as well as obstacles in inadequate school facilities and infrastructure.

Keywords: Leadership, Teacher, Employees

1. Introduction

As it is realized that schools are one type of organization that is often called a formal education organization (Kairienè, 2018), (Tamburlini, 2018). One of the most important organizational elements is the human, the internal personnel of the school organization consisting of the principal, teachers, students and school administration staff, the main activity they do is teaching and learning activities.

Indonesia, which provides education, certainly has its own philosophy and ideology in developing the world of education. The government through the Ministry of National Education as the representative of the government, has more responsibility for education in Indonesia, continues to strive to carry out and develop and improve the quality of National Education with its own interpretation.

In order for the school education process to be good, of course it requires qualified teaching staff who have high loyalty and discipline. High discipline will be very helpful in achieving goals, while to create a condition of discipline it is necessary to have a leader who is truly competent in carrying out his duties and responsibilities in carrying out school management, namely the work process with and through other people to achieve organizational goals efficiently (Andayani & Tirtayasa, 2019). Development and adoption of effective solutions for increasing demand and allocation of resources to develop and implement innovations that will improve school leadership (Moolenaar et al., 2010). Low teacher work discipline can result in the low quality of education in schools. The better the teacher's discipline, the higher the work performance he can achieve (Sudirman et al., 2020). Workplace discipline has a significant impact on employee behavior, which in turn has an impact on employee performance (Tentama et al., 2020).

However, to create this condition, it seems that there is still a need for a process so that school principals can improve the work discipline of employees and teachers. This can be seen from the results of temporary observations at SMA Negeri 2 Lahat, there are indications that lead to low work discipline of employees and teachers. (Moolenaar et al., 2010) said while school improvement efforts are more likely to succeed in a climate that supports innovation, the need for leadership behaviors that foster such a climate is often overlooked. Most reform-related policies focus on the technical elements of reform, and therefore many reform efforts in underperforming systems focus on program loyalty, rigid curricula, and a prescriptive approach. Teacher performance must be considered because the level of discipline can affect the quality, quality, and performance of teachers who do not meet existing standards. Personality, work knowledge, level of discipline, and honesty can all contribute to high performance (Nugraheni et al., 2020).

Some of the findings of low discipline in the workforce of employees and teachers include; Do not come to work without clear information, Neatness in the use of uniforms that have been determined by the school. During the teaching and learning process there are teachers who are not there. Come to school and go home before the time set by the school.

Based on the description above, the work discipline of teachers and employees must be improved to be even better. Realizing the importance of work discipline in order to achieve the vision and mission in schools, a good leadership role is needed in improving the work discipline of teachers and employees. With this description, the authors are interested in choosing the title *The Role of Principal Leadership in Improving Teachers and Employees Work Discipline*.

2. Methods

The type of research used in this research is descriptive qualitative research. The locations in this research are SMA Negeri 2 Lahat, Data Collection Technique; Library research, field research, Observation, Interviews, Document Studies and Documentation. The data analysis technique used in this study was the interactive model data analysis proposed by Miles and Huberman, namely by collecting data, simplifying data, presenting data, drawing conclusions.

3. Results and Discussion

The Role of Principal Leadership The principal is the highest leader in the school he leads. His leadership pattern will be very influential and will even determine the progress of the school. Principal leadership is the principal's way or effort in influencing, encouraging, guiding, directing, and mobilizing teachers, staff, students, parents and other related parties to work or participate in efforts to achieve predetermined goals. The principal as a leader will certainly have the ability or skills that support his ability as a leader in school such as good communication

skills, technical skills in his field, sharp analytical skills, assertiveness and courage to make decisions, high work ethic and have a clear vision (Akhadiyah et al., 2019)

The position of the principal is the highest leader and must supervise, protect all human resources in the school. In this role, the principal is responsible for the implementation of the entire education process in schools carried out by all elements of the school community. As a leader, it is natural that the principal is required to strive for the implementation of the education process effectively and efficiently. In carrying out his duties, a school principal has several important functions or roles. Apart from being a leader, the role of the principal in relation to the achievement of institutional goals is as a manager, as an administrator, as an educator, the principal must also be able to mobilize all school members, both teachers, students, parents of students, the community and educational facilities to achieve educational goals.

The principal in carrying out his duties needs to have leadership principles. Principles of principal leadership include constructive, creative, participative, cooperative, delegative, integrative, rational and objective. The existence of school principals at every level of education is very important. With the centralization of school authority in the hands of the principal, the school becomes a central feature as the highest leader and determines the success of the school in achieving the expected goals. The existence of school principals in relation to the success of achieving educational goals is largely determined by school management. Successful school management is largely determined by the leadership of the school principal. The existence of the principal is closely related to the ability to manage the school.

Duties and responsibilities are things that must be carried out by someone in holding a position. Likewise with the duties and responsibilities of the principal. The principal is an educational leader who has a very big role in developing the quality of education in schools. The development of work spirit, harmonious cooperation, interest in educational development, a pleasant working atmosphere and the development of professional quality among teachers are largely determined by the quality of the principal's leadership. Thus the principal is one of the keys to the success of the school in achieving its goals.

From the above statement it is clear that the principal is able to carry out his role as a leader in SMA Negeri 2 Lahat, it is proven that the principal has been able to formulate and determine school goals that the school will achieve and decide on the plan by meeting and receiving suggestions or input from existing teachers and employees. in school.

The principal as manager, the role of the principal as a manager in influencing teachers to achieve the desired school goals, improve performance, utilize all school resources to improve the vision, mission and achievement of goals. The principal requires each subject teacher to carry out a learning process that refers to graduation standards and to carry out subject teacher deliberations in schools to have adequate management and leadership skills in order to be able to take initiatives and initiatives to improve school quality. The principal can conduct deliberations to correct weaknesses that may occur in the school in the teaching and learning process (Moolenaar et al., 2010). After the ceremony, every Monday encourages the teachers to carry out their duties and work with a sense of responsibility and can achieve the school goals that have been set together, from this it is evident that the principal has done it to be able to inspire enthusiasm. teachers and employees in order to carry out their work. Even though as a teacher who gets additional assignments, the principal is the person most responsible for implementing innovative educational administration principles in schools. As a person who gets additional assignments, it means that the principal duty of the school is a teacher, namely as a teacher and educator. The principal of the school implements and provides lessons or teaches a particular field of study.

Turning to managerial concepts, managerial is an adjective related to leadership and management. In many literatures, the word managerial is often referred to as the origin of the word management which means to train a horse or literally means to handle which means to take care, handle, or control.

Meanwhile, management is a noun which can mean management, management or management. In principle, the notion of management has the following characteristics: there is a goal to be achieved; as a blend of science and

art; is a systematic, coordinated, cooperative and integrated process in utilizing its elements; there are two or more people working together in an organization; based on the division of labor, duties and responsibilities; includes several functions; is a tool to achieve goals. Management is a process of managing existing resources which has four functions of planning, organizing, mobilizing, and controlling activities carried out to achieve predetermined goals through the use of human resources and other resources.

In this regard, the duties and responsibilities of the principal are planning, organizing, directing, coordinating, supervising and evaluating all school activities, which include the areas of the teaching and learning process, office administration, student administration, employee administration, equipment administration, financial administration, library administration, and public relations administration. Therefore, in order to achieve organizational goals, the principal basically has the duty and responsibility to plan, organize, mobilize, and supervise all existing resources and activities carried out in schools.

The principal in that position functions as an Educator, Manager, Administrator, Supervisor. However, what will be discussed is in the field of Office Managers, the principal has duties and responsibilities. The principal works with, and through others, the notion of others, not only teachers, staff, students, and parents of students, but includes the principal's superiors, other school principals and other parties who need to connect and cooperate. The principal is responsible and accountable, the success and failure of subordinates is a direct reflection of the success or failure of the principal.

With limited time and resources, the principal must be able to face various problems, with all the limitations the principal must be able to arrange assignments appropriately. The principal must think analytically and conceptually, this function means that the principal must be able to solve the problem through an analysis, then solve the problem with a feasible solution. The principal as a mediator, in the school environment as an organization, in which there are people who have different backgrounds; temperament, education and social background. So that it is possible for a dispute to occur, here the principal must intervene as a mediator or mediator.

The principal as a politician, as a politician, means that the principal must always try to improve organizational goals and develop programs far ahead. The principal is a diplomat, in the role of a diplomat in various meetings the principal is the official representative of the school he leads. Difficult decision makers, if there are difficulties such as: funds, persistent employees, differences of opinion, the principal is expected to play a role as a person who can solve these difficult problems.

In carrying out his duties as an office manager, a principal must have 3 skills is Technical skills, Mastering knowledge about methods, processes, procedures and techniques for carrying out special activities, Ability to utilize and utilize facilities and infrastructure to support these special activities. Human skills, the ability to understand human behavior in the process of cooperation, the ability to understand the hearts, attitudes and motives of others, the ability to communicate clearly and effectively, the ability to create effective, cooperative, practical, diplomatic, and acceptable behavior Public. Conceptual skills, analytical skills, ability to think rationally, experts and proficient in various conceptions, able to analyze various kinds of events, able to anticipate various orders, able to recognize various kinds of opportunities and social problems (De Grauwe, 2005), (Memisoglu, 2015).

In addition to the above abilities, a school principal must be able to generate enthusiasm for all staff, teachers and students in achieving the goals that have been set and the principal must also be able to provide advice and input. The principal is an educator, while educating is defined as providing training (teachings, leadership) regarding morals and intelligence so that education can be interpreted as the process of changing the attitude and behavior of a person or group of people in an effort to mature humans through teaching and training efforts (Husna, 2017) as an educator, the principal must be able to instill, advance and increase four kinds of values, namely; Mental, matters relating to human attitudes and character, Moral, matters relating to good and bad teachings regarding actions, attitudes and obligations or moral, Physical, matters relating to the condition of the body or body, health and human appearance Artistic, matters related to human sensitivity to art and beauty.

So the things that need to be considered by a school principal as an educator include two main things, namely the target or to whom the behavior as an educator is directed and how the role as an educator is carried out. Therefore, there are three main targets, namely teachers or other functional personnel, administrative staff and students or students. In addition to the three main targets for implementing the role of the principal as educator, there are also other target groups that are no less important, namely parents' organizations, student organizations, and teachers' organizations.

The existence of parents' organizations is more needed to help and overcome the needs of various resources in fostering the life of school principals, both in the form of funds, facilities, services and thoughts as well as helping the implementation of student development, especially the implementation of programs outside the curricular. Student organizations are needed in an effort to provide a forum for students to grow and develop various interests, talents, and creativity through co-curricular programs, as well as outside the curricular as well as in an effort to support the success of curricular programs.

According to the author's interview with 10 teachers and employees, the role of the principal as an educator in SMA Negeri 2 Lahat is an important element in improving the teaching and learning process in schools, therefore teachers are expected to be creative educators, highly motivated and noble. All of this can be achieved if the teacher in carrying out the task gets satisfaction in his work. If their needs are met, the teacher will have positive values and attitudes in carrying out their work aimed at getting better education.

The principal in the teaching and learning process at SMA Negeri 2 Lahat uses the question and answer method, assignments and discussions, with question and answer the principal hopes that the method applied in the school can train students' courage to submit opinions that exist in students besides that by question and answer school principals also hopes that students can exchange knowledge with teachers and other students so that it will strengthen the relationship between students and subject teachers. With the assignment of the principal hopes to be able to train students to have a sense of responsibility and be able to do the tasks that the teacher gives students, by fostering a sense of responsibility the principal hopes that students will have a sense of responsibility until graduation, until college or the world of work and in the life that will continue in society.

As principal educators, they are required to provide role models for teachers, employees, students and citizens in good behavior. The success of a leader can be seen from the productivity and achievements he has achieved and judged by his kindness in relation to the implementation of his activities at school, therefore it is necessary to create an effective and good-minded leader. This shows that the principal's function as an educator is always to provide guidance and role models to teachers, employees, students, and other school members. As an educator, the principal must be able to instill, promote and improve at least four kinds of values. First, mental coaching related to the role of the principal in fostering education staff on matters related to mental attitudes and character. In this case the principal must be able to create a conducive climate so that every educational staff can carry out their duties properly, proportionally and professional (Hermino & Humanities, 2021). For this reason, the principal must try to complete the facilities, infrastructure and learning resources in order to make it easier for teachers to carry out their teaching duties. Second, moral coaching related to the role of the principal in fostering education personnel related to good and bad teachings regarding actions, attitudes, and obligations in accordance with the duties of each educational staff.

Understanding the meaning of educators is not enough by adhering to the connotations contained in the definition of educators, but must be studied in relation to the meaning of education, educational goals, how educational strategies are implemented. The lexical meaning or definition of educators is someone who educates, is educating which means providing training (teachings, leadership) regarding morals and intelligence so that education can be interpreted as a process of changing attitudes and behavior of a person or group of people in an effort to mature humans through teaching and practice (Husna, 2017) the principal's efforts to improve teacher performance, especially related to learning activities, can be described in three activities. First, guiding teachers, especially in matters related to planning and implementing learning programs, assessing student learning outcomes, analyzing learning assessment results and developing enrichment programs and learning

improvement. Second, the ability to give examples of good learning models, by analyzing subject matter, annual programs, semester programs, and learning programs or study units, as well as developing a list of student scores. Third, the principal is required to have the ability to provide an alternative model of effective learning by utilizing a variety of learning methods and resources. Based on the description above, a school principal as an educator must be a role model for teachers, staff and students.

As a school principal educator tries to humanize humans through fostering mental and moral values in matters relating to discipline, honesty, responsibility, friendship, flexibility, and so on. Besides that, the principal must also be able to be an example, have an interest in quality, and work with a foundation of good human relations. The principal as an administrator, namely, the principal must be able to master his duties and carry out his duties properly (Afrita et al., 2018).

The principal must be creative in order to be able to have ideas and initiatives that support school development. Various tasks that must be carried out include planning, compiling annual school programs, teaching programs, student affairs, staffing, finance, and providing the necessary facilities. This plan is then stated in the school's annual plan which is translated into a two-semester program.

The principal is required to understand and manage the curriculum, student administration, facilities and infrastructure administration, and archival administration. These activities need to be carried out effectively so that school administration can be well organized and carried out. As a committee member, it is also related to finance, that to achieve increased teacher competence cannot be separated from the cost factor. In managing this field, school principals must be careful, honest and open so that no suspicion arises from both staff and the community and parents of students (Perkins-Jacobs, 2015). From the results of the research that the author conducted with 10 teachers and employees at SMA Negeri 2 Lahat, they are required to be able to plan activities to be carried out and adjusted in financial administration in this school. which will be held in schools must be able to prioritize what is more important and urgent to be implemented such as completing what is lacking in schools such as books in the library that are still incomplete.

However, in this case the principal has not been able to carry out his role as administration properly, it is evident that the principal has not been able to be transparent in discussing financial administration, not all teachers and employees are involved in discussing financial administration so that it can cause social jealousy that may occur in the school environment. Thus the principal must be more transparent and able to complete the missing needs by using financial administration that is more expedient and open to all teachers and employees at SMA Negeri 2 Lahat.

The principal becomes a motivator to encourage being active and able to carry out his work in accordance with the established methods and procedures, because with the motivation given by the principal, teachers and employees will feel motivated or enthusiastic to carry out their duties and work well. Full of responsibility and can achieve the goals that have been determined together. In its role as a motivator, the principal must understand that motivation is a very important part of the school, teachers and employees will work seriously if they have high motivation (Finnigan, 2015). If teachers and employees have positive motivation, then teachers and employees will show more interest, concern and want to participate in assignments and work. In other words, teachers and employees will carry out their duties properly if there is a high motivation or encouragement factor from the principal (Amankwah & Hua, 2020). The principal always provides motivation and enthusiasm for the teacher to be able to deal with students who have different behaviors, meaning that the principal must be able to motivate the teacher to always be patient and steadfast because he faces students who certainly have standard behavior. thoughts in receiving different lessons, therefore the principal must pay more attention to the teacher in providing motivation in order to achieve the school goals that have been determined together.

The role of the principal as a motivator is to provide motivation to all school members so that they can carry out their duties at school properly and correctly. The ability of the principal as a motivator can be seen from the ability of the principal to regulate the work environment at school, the ability to regulate the work atmosphere so that the work atmosphere becomes comfortable and can lead to creativity and bright ideas from school residents.

The ability of the principal to regulate the work environment includes managing the physical environment of the school, managing office space that is conducive to work, managing classrooms that are conducive to teaching and learning activities, managing a school yard that is cool and orderly, facilitating school facilities and infrastructure to support productivity. work, and manage library space that is conducive to learning.

The principal's ability to regulate the work atmosphere includes creating a harmonious work relationship with fellow teachers, creating a harmonious relationship between the school and its environment, creating an atmosphere of togetherness at school, providing regular direction and guidance, understanding the tasks that must be done by each teacher. , provide moral support to teachers who have problems at work, and create order and a sense of security in schools. Building on the principles of reward and punishment, according to (Tangen, 2021) with appreciation, employees will be stimulated to increase positive and productive activities. Awards will be meaningful if they are openly linked to employee performance so that every employee has the opportunity to achieve it. Meanwhile (Wondal et al., 2019) explained that the application of punishment is intended to reduce and eliminate the possibility of unwanted behavior being repeated. Building the principles of reward and punishment includes giving proper rewards to teachers who excel, recognizing and appreciating every achievement that the teacher makes, 28 giving warnings when teachers do not complete their assigned tasks on time, giving warnings to teachers who come late or don't go to class, give a warning if the teacher does not come to work without permission, the teacher's work that is deemed good is shown to other teachers as a reference, provides criticism if the teacher's work is considered bad, and provides strict punishment to teachers who violate the rules.

Obstacles Faced by the Principal in Increasing the Work Effectiveness of Teachers and Employees. The principal of SMA Negeri 2 is bad in carrying out his role, namely the lack of teacher discipline in terms of the school schedule, because there are still teachers who pick up their children from school and leave lessons that have been carried out at school, besides that there are also teachers who bring their children to school. school so that it can interfere with the teacher's teaching time. In dealing with this, the principal has verbally reprimanded but there are still teachers who repeat it on the grounds that their children are alone at home.

The school principal also encountered obstacles in terms of advice and infrastructure that was still lacking at SMA Negeri 2 Lahat because he saw that the success of the education program through the teaching and learning process was strongly influenced by many factors, one of which was the availability of adequate educational facilities and infrastructure along with proper utilization and management. optimal. Educational facilities and infrastructure are one of the important and main resources in supporting the learning process in schools, therefore it is necessary to increase their utilization and management.

The lack of facilities and infrastructure owned by SMA Negeri 2 Lahat, including electricity that has not met the needs needed by the school so that schools need a generator engine (light machine) to meet school needs, a lack of textbooks / reading books that are still lacking in the library and the absence of a unit. School Health (UKS), this is the duty of the principal which is no less important to fulfill it.

Conclusion

The principal principal in SMA Negeri 2 Lahat is responsible for making improvements and creation of a conducive environment can be achieved effectively. The principal as a manager in influencing teachers to achieve the desired goals. As the principal manager of the school must be willing and able to utilize all school resources in improving the vision, mission and achieving school goals. In other words, teachers and employees will do their job well if there is a high motivational factor from the head of school.

The obstacles faced are teachers and employees who are less disciplined in carrying out their duties and jobs, as well as constraints on facilities and infrastructure. It was found that the problem in the MGMP was not fully operational, the management and all MGMP leaders had to have a good attitude in working together to optimize the MGMP program for organizational resources, namely not all English teachers. Based on the background of this problem, we suggest to the South Sumatra Provincial Education Office to increase the socialization of

Government policies regarding the MGMP Program, especially for English subjects which are carried out in Senior High Schools. Lack of awareness of their active involvement in the subject teacher professional forum.

Steps that can be taken are providing teachers with clearer and more detailed knowledge and understanding about MGMP policies, increasing budget allocations for socialization so that activities can be carried out in accordance with predetermined goals and Involving all levels of teachers, school principals, and leadership elements in The Office of Education and Culture in order to formulate programs / activities so that the involvement and ideas of all stakeholder elements can be accommodated.

In connection with English Learning Management, the following problems were found: the mapped objectives had not been implemented optimally, the monitoring of MGMP activities had not been carried out continuously, and supervision had not been able to provide improvements in teacher administration. The author suggests that the South Sumatra Provincial Education Office can increase the work motivation of teachers, school principals, and supervisors. Steps that can be taken are to provide opportunities for teachers, school principals, and supervisors to get education, training and technical guidance related to their work, encourage teachers to make work innovations in order to improve the results of future programs / activities and increase cooperation. Both inside and outside the work environment to strengthen relationships between teachers of other subjects.

The performance of English teachers is found to be constrained, not all English teachers have made plans for meeting teaching and learning activities according to the academic calendar, not all English teachers who are members of the MGMP can provide an evaluation of student work so that students can find out their weaknesses, and lack of implementation current teaching methods. Based on the background of the problems in the performance of English teachers, the authors suggest that the South Sumatra Provincial Education Office can improve the quality of their knowledge and skills in order to be able to provide excellent service to their students. Steps that can be taken include building a sense of empathy for English teachers through various trainings and self-development motivation. Establishing teaching and learning standards as a service that must be implemented and implementing rewards and punishments for learning

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